

Refresh the Reasonable Expectation: The Key to the Modern Privacy Rules

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Introduction

Privacy is not only a notion enshrined in the law; it has a social dimension in a specific cultural context. But in any event, the privacy situations cannot be departed from individual expectations. In spite of all the differences in the understanding of “privacy,” we now have a shared context – to promote information flow and reuse; the personal information, protected by the right to privacy, becomes valuable and tradable, and the infringement of “data privacy” is commonly connected with an act of discrimination, defamation, or identity fraud. The connotation of privacy is changing in times of technological progress.

On the other hand, privacy in the digital world is facing challenges: the consent regime is criticized for its ineffectiveness and is threatened to be on the road to demise, transparency requirements are in a dilemma to solve the “paradox” that stems from the changing technology, and the tradeoff hidden behind a balancing of interests appears to lead to a compromise on individual privacy interest.

Without trading off the competing interests, I center on the balancing of values between the portability of data and privacy protection – to find a way to balance the two that are supposedly subject to individual autonomy. For this reason, this paper considers the feasibility of refining the concept of reasonable expectation of privacy, as a possible solution to foster autonomy, based on the legal practice in the US, EU and China.

To make explicit the “reasonable expectation” of privacy in modern society, this paper develops four consent-based contexts, not only to define *reasonable* and *unreasonable* in different consent-based contexts, but also to explore how much a consent is likely to determine individual’s privacy interest, and how much the defense of legitimate interests of controllers is likely to affect the utility of consent doctrine, which **makes the reasonable expectation approach a supplement for absence of consent, a correction for invalid consent, and a restriction for applicability of overriding legitimate interest.**

A clash: data privacy and data portability

With the establishment of data protection regulations throughout various countries, the contents and objects of the right to privacy, along with data protection, have been expanded and deepened; the benefits of free flow of information, is always weight

against the possible risks to individual privacy. Thus, as a threshold matter, we need to enquire about the meaning and scope of privacy in modern society.

1. Whether privacy requires “secrecy” as a prerequisite

Warren and Brandeis viewed “the right to privacy, as a part of the more general right to the immunity of the person, - the right to one's personality,”¹ and it is oriented toward values of liberty, while the continental privacy rights focus on the protection of personal dignity.²

Although American scholars have argued that American privacy laws should adopt dignity, a more positive freedom, as the underlying rationale of privacy protection,³ it is unclear whether the Fourth Amendment protects information intentionally disclosed to a third party, which arguably indicates individual impliedly waives his(her) privacy rights by exposure to the public.⁴ In a recent case, the Court invoked *Van Buren's* “gates-up-or-down inquiry”⁵ in *hiQ v. LinkedIn*, reinforcing the significance of an authentication system for determining whether it is a publicly available website, where the users shall not maintain an expectation of privacy.⁶ Therefore, it remains doubtful that the information that is of public nature can be subject to a reasonable expectation of privacy.

In contrast, privacy in the European context does not focus on the “secrecy.” The Court has ever noted that an interaction of a person with others in a public context, may fall within the scope of “private life”; for example, the creation of a permanent record of the actions of an individual in a public place, was regarded as the processing of personal data, amounting to an interference with his(her) private life.⁷ The protection of privacy is embodied in EU data protection legislation, while the General Data Protection Regulation (hereinafter “GDPR”) establishes and develops the individual right to data protection, for the purpose of preventing potential harms to the essence of a fundamental right or of the constitutional order.⁸ Both privacy and data protection are enshrined in the European Convention for Human Rights (ECHR) and the EU Charter for Fundamental Rights (EUCFR).

In China, the Civil Code of China enshrines both the right to privacy and the right to personal data protection in Personality Rights (Book Four Chapter VI), prescribing that “privacy is the undisturbed private life of a natural person and his private space, private activities, and private information that he does not want to be known to others,” and “the provisions on the right to privacy...shall be applied to the *private* personal information.” Privacy is determined on a subjective base despite the adoption of “private” instead of “secret” – privacy is the information that an individual “does not *want* to be known.” But in practice, privacy is mostly conceived as the information that is *de facto not* disclosed to others, including an open web. For example, in the personalized advertising cases where a user’s browsing activity is acquired by the platform for advertising purpose, the tacit consent would be considered a voluntary exposure.⁹ While in the cases relating to a processing (transfer) of personal comments, the comments displayed on the platform might be treated as a creation of copyright (or at least fruits of labor) that is jointly owned by the platform and the data subject, but nothing related to the privacy.¹⁰ Thus, China’s legislation and legal practice seem to establish privacy on a non-publicly-

available premise.

However, it comes up with two concerns if we treat secrecy as a prerequisite for data privacy: (i) should we count on the third-party criteria to determine whether individuals *subjectively* waived their right to privacy? (ii) is there any privacy risk for those private-but-not-secret information?

To explicate individuals' subjective expectations toward privacy may be the key to the first question, but it varies with contexts. Taking the age as an example, the female may regard it as a secret, but not the male. But what a rational person can expect is that their information would be utilized in deference to their preferences for commercial purposes, and what a rational person cannot expect is that they cannot reject (or the rejection is futile) if they are unwilling to grant access to it. On this ground, this paper proposes to refresh the "reasonable expectation" approach to redefine the meaning and scope of privacy in the digital age.

For those private-but-not-secret information, the Internet browsing history stored in the cookies for instance, which the consumers knowingly expose to an open web, might be collected unwittingly, as shown in *Facebook Internet Tracking Litigation*¹¹ - it is unfair to require users to anticipate the processing beyond what they have agreed to. In addition, the aggregate data, obtained by assembling personal information without identifying particular individuals, has been criticized for its potential harms and lack of protection;¹² it harms individual's personality interests by using the shared characteristic data to create a predictive model to apply to each consumer in the same group, and even use it for unlawful discriminatory purposes.¹³ **Individual's privacy interest is thus harmed in an unexpected manner.**

2. Whether we should distinguish privacy in the digital world from the traditional view of privacy

To begin with, data privacy and privacy in the offline world are related yet distinct concepts. Professor Jerry Kang has argued that privacy is composed of three overlapping clusters: spatial privacy (physical space), decisional privacy (choice) and information privacy (flow of information).¹⁴ According to professors Koop [et al.], the "physical" layer of privacy, including bodily, spatial, communicational, proprietary, intellectual, decisional, associational and behavioral privacy, is distinguished from and each overlapping with the informational layer of privacy.¹⁵

In the US, the courts have confronted with the problems arising from modern surveillance tools.¹⁶ The challenges mainly lie in two aspects: (i) how to adjust the application of the third-party doctrine to digital data; (ii) to response to the digital age, whether the privacy expectation should be extended to the information in the public context. In the case of *Jones*, Justice Sotomayor noted that the third-party doctrine was "ill suited to the digital age."¹⁷ While in legislation, legislative action (e.g., the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA)) indicates society's willingness to extend an expectation of privacy to private-but-not-secret information.¹⁸

Taking the governmental searches as an example, the situation where the police work to find concealed drugs in a traditional non-digital manner should be distinguished

from data privacy in modern society. And moreover, the data privacy may go beyond “the other side of the coin” – the information about the physical layer of privacy (e.g., body, space, behaviors, etc.), and may target one’s reputation, property, or a fair chance.

It comes to a further question about whether the scope of privacy in cyberspace could be extended to data processing activities in relation to infringement on other individual rights, including discrimination, defamation and identity fraud, etc. Given that discriminatory practices do not always give rise to violations of individual dignity; discrimination touches more on “fair chance,”¹⁹ some commentators, in an EU context, argued that a processing of personal data can have consequences in terms of discrimination, which is not the issue of privacy,²⁰ data protection is thus broader than privacy in this sense. Despite some disagreements over the “almost universal consensus” across the EU that data protection legislation exists largely to protect privacy, privacy does occupy a central place in data protection.²¹

This paper argues that the data privacy is commonly infringed for the purpose of, or by virtue of discrimination, defamation, or identity theft, pertaining to overarching individual interests. For example, the use of big data can injure the civil rights of the poor in the fields of employment, education and housing - profiling the poor in ways that limit their employment and educational opportunities,²² or subject them to discrimination in application for a loan.²³ The contents and objects of the right to privacy have been expanded and deepened.

The notion of data privacy has shaped the modern privacy rules, and individuals’ right to privacy should come under the spotlight in data protection. For the purpose of endowing personal data with tradability, we need to acknowledge individuals’ property interests in his(her) own personal data, but it should be restricted to the extent that individuals’ privacy interests are not interfered. The privacy tort should preempt the property rights held by the data subject or data controller.²⁴ In other words, when the privacy interests of data subject or other natural persons are damaged or probably damaged due to transfer,²⁵ **it should be given priority to the invasion of privacy claims** and, as such, the “reasonable expectation of privacy” can be approached to balance the privacy protection with data portability. But there is an exception – the privacy claim shall not be brought where the data cannot be recognized as personal data, or constitutes the intellectual property held by the controller.

3. Whether we should distinguish the online invasion of privacy from the offline cases

This concern arises from the legal practice when dealing with the cases where there is inequality of power between the digital platforms and the users. In practice, the disputes over whether a digital platform interferes with one’s privacy or right to data protection unlawfully, often involve with the conflicts of interests between platforms, or the impacts on the competition order. The unfair competition law (e.g., *biQ v. LinkedIn*, *Dianping v. Baidu Map* (China)), or antitrust (e.g., *Facebook v. Bundeskartellamt*),²⁶ may thus apply to these situations in which the focus will be shifted from whether there is a violation of right to privacy, to whether the competitive interests, or even property

interests of the controller, deserve a protection by the law.

But can we resort to the modern privacy rules to solve the dispute of data use in the “user-platform-user/platform” context? In short, is the privacy rule (data protection rule in a broader sense) a more effective legal tool to enable the portability of data while maintaining individuals’ control? It needs to elaborate on how the reasonable expectation test will perform this function in a competitive environment in the next part.

A solution: reasonable expectation of privacy

1. Theory: reasonable expectation under “contextual integrity”

What is at stake in discussion of data privacy? Put simply, it concerns with control, transfer and technological innovation.

In some literatures, data privacy is used to describe data protection,²⁷ but it is not only “to be let alone,” but also “positive freedom,”²⁸ which means informational self-determination, namely, the individual is able to freely decide how to live his(her) life. Meanwhile, the development of data gathering and processing techniques, such as aggregation, profiling, location tracking, facial recognition, etc., questions the effectivity of the traditional rules, such as consent-based rules, third-party rule, property transfer rules, which are mostly challenged due to information flows.

In such settings, the contextual integrity (hereinafter “CI”) theory wins itself a place in the digital era. Unlike the notice and choice approach, which is criticized for its ineffectiveness in addressing the countervailing interests,²⁹ or the data ownership approach, which is dependent on the consent and control system,³⁰ or the purpose limitation principle, which struggles with the “business interest priority” clause (e.g., “overriding legitimate interest” in GDPR,³¹ establishing a test database for securing user data may be justified;³² “business purpose” in CPRA), the CI theory focuses on the information flow that respects contextual information norms.³³

However, there is great variability in the aspects of contexts and its relationship with the information in question. Can it only be subjected to the judiciary, or can it be specified in writing? **This paper considers the feasibility to combine the reasonable expectation of privacy with the consent-based rules – to define the “reasonable expectation” in different consent-based contexts.**

There is context-relative variation in the information gathering and dissemination, which is a question to be answered; drawing a line for this variation by refining the concept of reasonable expectation of privacy, is a possible solution – where we need value tradeoffs and how to evaluate them, what rules control the variation (appropriateness and flow) - is more than variability.

This paper explores how to determine the “reasonable expectation” based on the “user-platform-user/platform” model. For example, an open-source decentralized social media platform, Mastodon, is taking in users who are seeking Twitter alternatives.³⁴ Despite the absence of a corporation that controls user data, and an algorithm that profiles users, it is still uncertain whether the “newcomer” will prevail for its “privacy flag.” However, it represents a significant model for the relationship between

data privacy and data portability – privacy expectation in a competitive environment – people’s data will flow to some “platform,” which serves as an intermediary or a terminal, and thus to connect with other people or other platforms.

1.1. to explore the function of CI theory

To begin with, we can explore the function of CI theory – it may be of great significance to be a supplement for absence of consent, a correction for invalid consent, and a restriction for applicability of overriding legitimate interest.

For example, when a user claims his right to data portability for his(her) “social graph”³⁵ on a social media platform, can it be transferred as a whole? There are several contexts to be considered – when the “third person” involved agrees or he(he) does not suffer privacy damage due to the transfer (e.g., sufficient technological protection is in place), it could be transferred; when the “graph” is protected by the intellectual property right (hereinafter “IPR”), it cannot be transferred at will; however, when the data constitutes competitive resources, and to encourage newcomers will increase consumer choice, the transfer could be reasonable even if the data is protected by IPR.

The above considerations conform to the CI theory, but we can get back to a more fundamental question: what if the user consent is absent, or the user consents but conflicts with the controller's legitimate interest? It follows that we need to adapt the theory to the notice-and-choice paradigm and legitimate interest defense.

1.2. to contextualize the consent

The consent doctrine is closely related to individuals’ privacy expectations via the “third-party doctrine.” When a person knowingly exposes his(her) information to a third party, it can be understood as a consent,³⁶ but he(he) does not necessarily lose his(her) privacy expectation - consent to a company’s user agreement or privacy policy for data collection does not amount to consent to reuse or use in an unexpected way, such as a warrantless search.³⁷ Thus, the consent doctrine seems to be more straightforward and precise than the third-party doctrine in the digital world.

Nevertheless, scholars criticized the hardships in recognizing genuine “knowing and voluntary” consent - professors Richards and Hartzog pointed out the defects in the consent models - unwitting consent, coerced consent, and incapacitated consent.³⁸ In this respect, the conceptualization of reasonable expectation of privacy might be a redress to the consent models, to maximize the utility of the consent doctrine.

The reasonable expectation test can be a supplement for absence of consent, including some “unwitting consent.” For example, the platform may claim its legitimate interest for the aggregate data and thus reuse it without user consent. It can strengthen our sense of security about our data if we are certain about whether it is *unreasonably* expected even absent a separate consent. Second, the model of “privacy expectation in a competitive environment” can deal with the inequality in power between platform and user, or among platforms.

Therefore, this paper argues that the choice of opt-in or opt-out may be decided by the norms of appropriateness, but whether it (the consent) fails is decided by the privacy expectation, and **the consent can be contextualized to determine whether a data processing is in line with individual’s reasonable expectations of privacy** (hereinafter “REP”).

1.3. how to contextualize the consent

Platform operators call for consumer consent, as a routine, to reasonably process individuals' data. However, consumers may not notice the “opt-out” option provided by the company, which is the reason why many people do not feel that they have ever consented. Thus, we should enquire about whether it is a valid consent in the opt-out context, but what if consumers positively opt out in such circumstances? Does the opt-in context indicate the same individual expectation of privacy? Under what conditions can a consumer's decision be considered consistent with his(her) expectation?³⁹

Without distinguishing the situations where surveillance is conducted in public or not, I argue **four consent-based contexts in a competitive environment**:

- (i) valid user opt-in for data scraping in opt-out context – **technological progress and chance to reject**. There is a valid tacit consent in cases where, for example, a third-party scraps user data in a publicly-available platform, and user does not reject; the consistency with REP originates from what you can benefit from and have come to expect, on a notice-and-choice base – means you have chance to reject.
- (ii) valid user opt-out for data scraping in opt-out context – **what deserves a heightened level of scrutiny**. There is a valid rejection in cases where a third-party scraps user data in a publicly-available platform, and user positively rejects in response to controller's announcement, not general terms; the consistency with REP originates from what you specially care, such as the “deeply revealing” information about families, religion, health, etc.⁴⁰
- (iii) invalid user opt-in for data processing in opt-in context – **lock-in effect**. There is NOT a valid consent in cases where the user is locked in to the platform, and user positively agrees to processing; the inconsistency with REP originates from what you are entitled to but fail to choose. The platform just attempts to be “privacy-friendly” by adopting opt-in mode.
- (iv) invalid user opt-out for data processing in opt-in context – **lack of cost transparency**. There is NOT a valid consent for data processing in cases where there is lack of transparency in the hidden costs of techniques applied to privacy protection, such as subscription fees arising from ad-diminishing, costs arising from standardization, and user positively consents or rejects to render the data without genuine “knowing”;⁴¹ the inconsistency with REP originates from what you are normally not informed of – the invisible “price terms.”

2. Practice: reasonable expectation in a competitive environment

The right to data privacy is incompatible with traditional property rules, such as intellectual property rule,⁴² even when we talk about the right to controlling information flow (e.g., right to data portability). The fundamental controversy lies in who holds the right, and **how easy it is for the data subject to win the privacy claims**. Regardless of

whether the data subject holds a “quasi-property” interest in his(her) data, the business interest priority clause is much like the “fair use” in the intellectual property law – they both can free the platform from tort liability for a use without permission. Thus, we need to ensure that the invasion of privacy claims preempt property and liability claims.

The interest tradeoffs embedded in data protection laws inevitably compromise the priority of the right to informational self-determination in a sense. Some commentators argue that the balancing actually concerns the freedom (data protection) and the obligations that the controller fulfills to protect it.⁴³ In this respect, **the “reasonable expectation” of data privacy here aims to put a limit on the applicability of the legitimate interest defense.**

The significance of the right to data portability is to facilitate data portability while strengthening the individual control, which relies on user’s request for transfer. But there is practical problems - non-requesting cases,⁴⁴ where a natural person’s data is transferred without his(her) consent, or a third party requests for sharing but is denied by the controller (or the user), or a third party directly scraps user data without permission. By refreshing the function of reasonable expectations, this paper helps to fill the gap in these non-requesting cases.

However, regardless of whether the consent is absent or invalid, the interests claimed by the third party in the transfer, should be proven to be justified – the transfer is implemented in a form that does not release information covered by trade secrets or IP rights.⁴⁵

Based on the legal practice in the US, EU and China, the following four consent-based contexts explore four questions: (i) how the technological development can contribute to the publicity of data and interfere with individual’s private life in public; (ii) how the algorithms and profiling activities exert influence on individual’s privacy interest; (iii) whether the privacy expectation approach is more workable than the notice-and-choice paradigm, to tackle the “privacy paradox,” in cases where there is power differential; (iv) without any obscure language, how the invisible costs terms can influence the validity of consent, in the disguise of a “privacy-friendly” agreement.

2.1. Opt-out context: valid user opt-in for data scraping

In China, the disputes over the use of personal data in a public network, in relation to the interference with private interests of the controller, are usually resolved via liability claims under the Anti-Unfair Competition Law (hereinafter “AUCL”).

In *Dianping v. Baidu Map*,⁴⁶ Dianping.com, is a platform providing customer reviews and ratings of various businesses (e.g., local restaurants, shops; China’s equivalent of Yelp), and sued Baidu (a Chinese search engine operating an online mapping app “Baidu Map,” which displayed customer reviews when searching a place on the map) for misuse of data scraping - scraping massive amounts of raw data, i.e., customer reviews and ratings, from Dianping by technical means, and utilized the data for profit.

The Shanghai IP Court ruled that: (i) the amount of data, with high commercial value, scraped by the defendant, has violated the principle of minimisation, the content on Baidu Map’s website is proved to be a “substantive substitute” of that on Dianping’s website;⁴⁷(ii) the method caused deterrence in *business investment* in information collection, to the detriment of competition order; (iii) the same benefits could be achieved through

other means. Accordingly, the court ruled that Baidu had committed an act of unfair competition in violation of AUCL.

From the perspective of data protection, the reviews and ratings involved may arguably fall within the scope of personal information,⁴⁸ but the business investment added to the information gathering and data maintenance is treated as legitimate interest of the controller. This case raises a question: when the consumers expose themselves to a “public realm,” do they retain an expectation of privacy in their comments data, and is there a valid consent?

First, data scraping can be treated as a free-riding practice, and may fall within the scope of unfair competition law. In essence, the similarity between these two practices lies in the private claims over the business investment. But does the consumer lose his(her) right to reject?

It is out of question that we need to reward market players for their honest labor or efforts, but business investment is not a property right,⁴⁹ and individual’s right over personal information is not fully transferred along with the information flow,⁵⁰ by data subject consent (or acquiescence). To be specific, Dianping would not have a valid infringement claim in this context unless the data is a copyrighted work, and is assigned to the platform. Otherwise, the fruits of labor with high commercial value, generated from business investment, are freely ridden by competitors to the detriment of honest market player,⁵¹ which have to be balanced by the severity of the detriment. It follows that free-riding between individual platform owners without a decisive momentum, may be free of condemnation.

Among others, the “transformative” qualities could be an objective ground for justifying the free-riding, even if the original creation is protected by copyright. The U.S. Court of Appeals conducted a detailed analysis of the transformative nature of Google’s use of “thumbnail,” in the copyright infringement case *Perfect 10 v. google*, where the fair use defense raised by Google was affirmed.⁵² The thumbnail versions of Perfect 10’s images, derived from infringing websites in Google’s Internet-wide search engine activities and stored in Google’s servers, could be deemed a “transformative” work.

The “transformative” qualities are associated with some public benefit. The appellate court stated in its reasons for the decision that a work is “transformative” when the new work does not “merely supersede the objects of the original creation,” but rather “adds something new, with a further purpose or different character, altering the first with new expression, meaning, or message.”⁵³ The activity that a search engine incorporates an electronic reference tool fits the requirement of “transformative,” and “the significantly transformative nature of Google’s search engine, particularly in light of its *public benefit*, outweighs Google’s superseding and commercial uses of the thumbnails in this case.”

Second, the technological progress that takes the form in conformity with individual’s reasonable expectations of privacy, can be an objective ground for justifying personal data processing practice. According to the Guide to the General Data Protection Regulation (hereinafter “Guide”) issued by ICO (Information Commissioner’s Office of the UK), the decisive factors for finding a reasonable expectation of privacy, include whether there are any developments in technology or updates to services which individuals have come to expect.⁵⁴ On this ground, if the aforementioned

“transformative” qualities could be combined with other qualities that consumers *can benefit from*, such as convenience, efficiency, etc., and *can anticipate*, the applications of technology in the information gathering and dissemination will probably not be deemed an invasion of privacy. In *Dianping*, for instance, Baidu map incorporated the function of mapping and rating into the search results in the interest of consumers (including Dianping users), which is new but not unpredictable – consumers’ tacit consent to the transfer, retaining the right to reject, could be found valid. In this view, by applying the reasonable expectation test, the interests claimed by the third party in the transfer here – through data scraping, can be proven to be justified, and can prevail against the private interest of controller.

Therefore, guided by the rationale of balancing the portability of data with privacy protection, **the contexts where the platform adopts the technology that qualifies as transformative and consumers can benefit from and have chance to reject**, might be justified as consistent, with the individual’s privacy expectation.

2.2 Opt-out context: valid user opt-out for data scraping

Sometimes we may positively reject in the opt-out context, and it deserves a concern, even though the “technological progress” criteria in the first context is fulfilled. In this part, we will explore whether the users retain the privacy interests over the “public information” in cases like *hiQ v. LinkedIn* (hereinafter “LinkedIn”),⁵⁵ which will be compared to another case *Facebook v. Power Ventures*, as to the validity of user consent.

In *LinkedIn*, hiQ scrapes information that LinkedIn users have included on public LinkedIn profiles, including name, job title, work history, and skills. It sells a software “people analytics” based on that information to business clients. The most controversial part of the function of the software, is to alert employers and recruiters when LinkedIn users update their profile, an indication they may be about to switch jobs. LinkedIn employed various blocking techniques designed to prevent hiQ’s automated data collection methods, and threatened action under the Computer Fraud and Abuse Act (CFAA). HiQ therefore contends that LinkedIn’s actions constitute unfair business practices under Cal. Bus. & Prof. Code §§ 17200 et seq (i.e., California’s Unfair Competition Law, hereinafter “UCL”).

The balance of hardships tips in hiQ’s favor. In particular, the Court is doubtful that: (i) the data at issue is publicly available LinkedIn member profiles, the CFAA may not be invoked; (ii) LinkedIn may not be able to prove *private business interests* - protecting its members’ data and the investment made in developing its platform, and the privacy interests retained by some LinkedIn users do not outweigh hiQ’s interest in continuing its business; (iii) LinkedIn, in blocking hiQ’s access to public data, possibly as a means of limiting competition, violates the UCL. Finally, The Ninth Circuit affirmed the district court’s grant of a preliminary injunction in favor of hiQ, and affirmed its decision after the Supreme Court remanded for additional consideration.

In the meantime, the Court explained the reason why LinkedIn users did not maintain an expectation of privacy:⁵⁶

“First, there is little evidence that LinkedIn users who choose to make their profiles public, actually maintain an expectation of privacy,” according to the availability to the public statement in LinkedIn’s privacy policy. “Second, there is no evidence in the record

to suggest that most people who select the ‘Do Not Broadcast’ option do so to prevent their employers from being alerted to profile changes,⁵⁷” because “many users may simply wish to avoid sending their connections annoying notifications each time there is a profile change.”

The posting of changes to a profile may, at any rate, raise the risk that a current employee may be rated as having a higher risk of being recruited away, notwithstanding LinkedIn’s violation of its own privacy policy - LinkedIn conveyed its users’ information including profile changes to third parties as well.

However, different from *Dianping v. Baidu Map*, the nature of the data involved is more “deeply revealing” with regard to profiles – profiles that include a user’s real name, image, employment history, etc., and the attitude of the LinkedIn users is “positive rejection” by activating the “Do Not Broadcast” service. By contrast, in *Facebook v. Power Ventures*, the user data was scraped from a “private” social network that is protected by a password authentication system, and the Facebook users (also Power users) consented to Power’s access to their e-mail account on Facebook to disseminate promotional messages.

Facebook thus sued Power Ventures for its access to Facebook’s computers without permission. In clicking the “Yes, I do!” button on the icon placed on Power’s website, a Power user gave Power permission to share its promotion through event invitation, Power then accessed that user’s Facebook data and promoted its website by sending form e-mails to the user’s friends. The court held that Power had accessed Facebook computers “without authorization” and was therefore liable under the CFAA. But was the consent (to promotion) invalid due to the unavailability of the right or the infringement upon another person’s right? How about the privacy expectation of Facebook users in this case? Is “private” or “public” information the decisive factor for finding a reasonable expectation of privacy?

First, there is controversy over whether *Katz*’s “subjective expectation of privacy” test is still applicable to the digital world. As the Court stated in *Katz*⁵⁸, a person enjoys a Fourth Amendment protected interest if he/she has “exhibited an actual (subjective) expectation of privacy.”⁵⁹ But it should be socially recognized and accepted expectations of privacy at the same time; both the technological advancement and the legal practice (e.g., *Carpenter*⁶⁰) underlie the demise of the subjective test.⁶¹ As compared to the subjective test, GDPR seems to take an objective approach according to the Guide issued by ICO – whether the individual can reasonably expect the data processing is an objective test - “the question is not whether a particular individual actually expected the processing, but whether a reasonable person should expect the processing in the circumstances.”⁶²

This paper proposes to take into account an objective approach. In *LinkedIn*, the Court adopted a subjective standard based on the presumption that the users subjectively waived their right to privacy by revealing themselves to a public network. However, this may facilitate the establishment of the “walled gardens” - to prevent competitors from obtaining user information,⁶³ as well as to take in consumers in a “privacy-friendly” manner, while failing to describe accurately all relevant charges to the consumer when marketing a service.⁶⁴ On this ground, we should acknowledge that there is socially recognized expectations, and an individual harbors a reasonable expectation of privacy

for those private-but-not-secret information in the digital age, in particular, for those that he/she positively rejects to reveal.

Second, the purpose limitation principle should be activated to distinguish a secondary consent (including rejection, acquiescence) from the initial one – **whether each processing is in line with individual’s reasonable expectations pertains to the specific privacy protection measures that companies take and reveal in their policy, not the general terms.** However, there has been debates as to whether the information that is of public nature (e.g., phone numbers in published directories) is subject to a reasonable expectation of privacy.⁶⁵ In *LinkedIn*, LinkedIn’s privacy policy states that “[a]ny information you put on your profile and any content you post on LinkedIn may be seen by others,” but also provides “Do Not Broadcast” option for the user, users can thus opt into the feature to prevent the site from notifying other users when a member makes profile changes – they are likely to expect it to work. The Ninth Circuit affirmed the district court’s opinion that “the fact that a user has set his [social media] profile to public does not imply that he wants any third parties to collect and use that data for *all purposes*.”⁶⁶ Additionally, the fact that LinkedIn’s product enables recruiters to get “alert[ed] when prospects make changes to their profiles,” without their knowledge, to the detriment of users’ (privacy) interest, cannot be used to deny the users’ right to privacy however.

It follows that we cannot separate the “reasonable expectation” from the specific processing purpose behind *a specific announcement*, because any privacy protection measures or privacy settings announced by the company may influence a consumer’s decision to opt in or opt out. In *Power*, the password authentication system set by Facebook is just like a confidentiality commitment, and consumers may reasonably expect the security of their data accordingly. However, in *Facebook Internet Tracking Litigation*,⁶⁷ Facebook tracked users whenever they visited unaffiliated websites containing Facebook “like” buttons, and sold their profiles to advertisers for a profit, which violated its own data use policy stated in the “Help Center” - Facebook promised to stop the tracking once users logged out - Facebook set an expectation for the user, but failed to fulfill it. Hence, any commitment on the privacy protection measures in the data use policy, notwithstanding the public nature of user information revealed in general terms, plays a part in determining whether the individual would reasonably expect the processing to occur.

Last but not least, we should consider to raise the bar for determining the consistency with the reasonable expectation of privacy where there is use of sensitive personal information or automated profiling, to presume that individuals have a higher level of expectations in such circumstances. In *LinkedIn*, users knowingly and actively give away information about themselves to the platform, as compared to the information acquired by cookies, plug-ins on the website, etc., in a manner undetectable by the user - **the difference is not whether they expose it voluntarily, but how deeply they can expect the platform to reveal.**⁶⁸ In *Facebook Internet Tracking Litigation*, by correlating users' browsing history with users' personal Facebook profiles - profiles that could include a user's family life, employment history, political and religious affiliations - Facebook gained a cradle-to-grave profile without users' consent.

Therefore, irrespective of whether users intentionally make their information

available to a public network in accordance with the general terms, the individual's privacy expectation is related to **the contexts where a specific privacy protection measure is announced in the data use policy**. We need to subject the use of sensitive personal information and automated profiling to a heightened level of scrutiny, or even to establish a reverse onus – to presume that individuals have higher expectations in such settings, and this applies to both the controller and the third parties. Additionally, the consent mechanism still works in deference to individuals' expectations in the above cases, where the LinkedIn users explicitly reject in response to controller's announcement, and the Power users consent to the data use without justified expectation – it intruded upon a third person's privacy without her consent.

2.3. Opt-in context: invalid user opt-in for data processing

Our decision or behavior is not always consistent with what we genuinely expect. In this part, we will explore whether the privacy expectation approach is workable to tackle the “privacy paradox” – where consumers act in conflict with their stated privacy preferences.

In *Facebook v. Bundeskartellamt* (German Federal Cartel Office; hereinafter “German Facebook case”),⁶⁹ the Federal Court of Justice of Germany (Bundesgerichtshof, BGH) annulled the decision of the Düsseldorf Higher Regional Court on June 2020, in support of the decision rendered by the Bundeskartellamt, finding that Facebook requires users to agree to its terms of service that allow for the processing of user data generated outside the Facebook platform,⁷⁰ without users' further consent, which constituted an abuse of dominance, in violation of German Act against Restraints of Competition (GWB). The two courts disagreed over whether there was “coercion” behind the “privacy paradox” - the consent given by a Facebook prospect to the terms of use, in conflict with his(her) preferences, was a result of Facebook's market power, not the result of an individual assessment. The Federal Court of Justice held that “the lack of options available to Facebook users affected their personal autonomy and the exercise of their right to informational self-determination”; “Facebook's access to a considerably larger data base contributed to the interlinking and profiling of user data across various devices, platforms and websites, and thus increased the already distinct ‘lock-in effects.’” Thus, if competition on the market were effective, “this option could be *expected* to be available.”⁷¹

However, just as the Higher Regional Court stated in its decision that users' decision for or against Facebook primarily take into account the expected quality and the hoped-for personal benefit of the network, users' privacy expectations appear to coincide with what the platform has announced, by using their additional data – the terms of use specify that Facebook provides a personalized experience for each user. But the consent may be less legitimate and invalid where there is a coerced consent.⁷²

This paper explores to what extent a consent could be recognized as “coerced” – the coercion could be generated from the impediments to switching for consumers, where it would entail them (sometimes including the downstream partners) bearing high switching costs, even when consumers positively agree to processing. In this respect, we could **consider the contribution of inter-platform “rivalry” in the market to the conformity of consent with one's privacy expectation** – individuals will expect more

options where there is an impediment to switching. But it is noteworthy that the legitimacy of the interests claimed by the third party (here is the competitor), should be based on the premise that it does not result in an invasion of a third person's privacy, other than the data subject's consent or wish (e.g., the *Power* case) – **to intrude on others' privacy cannot be deemed a reasonable expectation.**

To sum up, the individual's privacy expectation is related to **the contexts where there is an impediment to switching** - users are locked in to the platform, irrespective of whether it runs in opt-in mode - individuals expect a competitive market to work to their benefit.

2.4. Opt-in context: invalid user opt-out for data processing

If we could opt out of a platform without any restrictions and impediments as shown in the above context, does it indicate that we are not “locked in” and can thus decide about the use of our data freely, uninfluenced and autonomously?

Different from the common transparency issues, such as the “designed obscurity” in the agreement or privacy notice,⁷³ the well-known “paradox of transparency,⁷⁴” and the advanced technology being agreed to (which has been discussed in the first and second contexts). This part will focus on how the lack of cost transparency will violate individual's reasonable expectations of privacy, under a privacy-friendly appearance – we may stay alert if we need to render our data, but we may lower our guard if we could easily rule it out, by preventing user tracking, or deidentifying; and the possible impacts on consumers, their privacy interests to be specific, are that they may pay the price for their own privacy without their even knowing it, and without any obligations imposed on the controller, to report the performance as a listed company should do – it appears to be a “free” service.

For example, Apple's new App Tracking Transparency feature (hereinafter “ATT”) requires third-party apps to get user's opt-in permission to collect their advertising identifier data to the prejudice of independent advertisers.⁷⁵ Concerning the impact of this policy, other than smaller brands, such as advertising company, mega digital platforms are also affected. Commentators have noted a shift away from ad spending at Facebook and Instagram to companies such as Google, Amazon, TikTok, and Walmart.⁷⁶ For similar purposes, Google launched “privacy sandbox” proposals to curb user tracking by blocking the third-party cookies, and only provide aggregate data to downstream adtech vendors.

Two problems might be worth noting here: (i) First-party data. Apple's ATT does not prohibit apps from collecting and using first-party data, which means the cross-site tracking would be allowed if those apps are owned by the same company.⁷⁷ And Google's sandbox also requires online publisher to remove third-party cookies and rely on the first-party data, which will make Chrome the central player in the adtech ecosystem.⁷⁸ Thus, the use of first-party data will contribute to a “closed” system, in favor of the large-scale companies.

(ii) Aggregation and real-time reporting. Apple only allows targeting of ads to large groups of users, which disables the identification of any particular user.⁷⁹ This is so-called “aggregation,” or “interest group targeting,” as a technique to reduce privacy risk, by algorithm that groups customers based on shared characteristic, e.g., browsing activity,

which can be used to predict consumers' behaviors. Google also provides aggregate report for advertising, as a replacement for third-party cookies. But it is not a real-time report, and will lose efficiency.

As a consequence, there are basically three options for the apps or websites to get refund for their loss of profit. The first one is to change their business models to levy a charge on consumers for subscribing to their services, for instance, rather than rely on advertising; the second one is to create user identifiers to provide a shared ID (universal ID solutions),⁸⁰ for establishing cross-site identity (based on encrypted e-mail or phone number) without relying on third-party cookies, but it is difficult for less-known brands to convince users to entrust them with their intimate information;⁸¹ and the third one is, just as the flow of the ad spending has indicated, to switch to another mega brand that boasts a large user base (e.g., Android), and employs the first-party data as well - another "closed" system given the exclusive nature of "first-party."

In the first and third scenario,⁸² **without sufficient data flows, the costs of techniques applied to privacy protection are likely to be passed on to consumers eventually, just as a sales tax would be.** It is unclear about the effectiveness of the privacy risk control, while consumers seem to pay for the "wall" without genuine knowing, and subsidize the "walled garden." Hence, those costs shall be subject to a reasonable expectation of privacy – the consent will be deemed invalid if the decision to opt in (or out) is not based upon an informed choice.

However, consumers may also pay for the flow of information without their knowledge. To establish harmonized standards for interoperability of data and data sharing mechanisms will also give rise to the cost transparency problem.

As stated in Recital 68 GDPR, "Data controllers should be encouraged to develop interoperable formats that enable data portability," but it does not mention any fees. In some sectors, key players, typically the Internet service providers, already provide their users with certain functionalities for exporting data,⁸³ whereas in other sectors, such as telecommunications, automotive industry, the implementation of standardization is confronting challenges (e.g., cybersecurity concerns of connected and automated cars).

In essence, the conflict of interest occurs between privacy and the incentive to innovate. Taking the automotive industry as an example. The technological solutions such as the interoperable on-board application platform, might lead to very high costs, such as transaction costs, for the platform owners to convince a sufficiently large number of car owners to opt in to the platform.⁸⁴ However, to develop a single interoperable platform requires huge investments. It is doubtful that the charges will not be imposed on the consumers since there is uncertainty about who has the ownership of the anonymized or deidentified in-vehicle data,⁸⁵ and many innovative services (e.g., remote diagnostics and maintenance) would be expected to be offered to car users, let alone the new expensive communication infrastructure - it is reasonable to get compensation for those "creation," just as to license IP rights. **The remuneration, just like royalty fee, shall be subject to a reasonable expectation of privacy.**

Generally speaking, consumers are likely to be far more sensitive to price terms, such as the cost of a checking account, than to nonprice terms like the privacy policies and practices.⁸⁶ However, as "privacy" becomes increasingly valuable in the digital age, to

act in a “privacy-friendly” manner (e.g., opt-in permission) could increase both the number of users and profits for companies, but consumers may become the ones that pay for the bills.

Therefore, all the costs and remuneration in relation to privacy protection that will fall on the consumer, shall be subject to a reasonable expectation of privacy. In keeping with this, companies should explain the hidden costs of services and techniques applied to privacy protection, because the invisible costs can influence individuals’ decision to opt into or turn off data sharing. Any consent or rejection without informed choices cannot be deemed valid. As such, **the contexts where the costs in relation to privacy protection are fully disclosed to the data subject**, might be justified as consistent, with the individual’s privacy expectation.

In conclusion, for the purpose of prioritizing individual’s right to informational self-determination, when balancing the portability of data against privacy protection, the reasonable expectation test could be applied as follows:

Privacy interests v. Competitive interests	Consistent with reasonable expectation (valid consent)	Inconsistent with reasonable expectation (invalid consent)	Higher expectation presumption
Free-riding (<i>Dianping</i> case)	Adoption of the technology that qualifies as transformative, and consumers can benefit from, and have chance to reject		
Technological access barrier (<i>LinkedIn</i> case)	Match between user-facing privacy practice/announcement and its internal conduct (e.g., “Do Not Broadcast” setting – to set an expectation)	Mismatch between user-facing privacy practice/announcement and its internal conduct; ⁸⁷ no opt-out option for the use of sensitive personal information or automated profiling	Use of sensitive personal information, or automated profiling ⁸⁸ (Stricter protection measures are recommended)
Lock-in effect (<i>German Facebook</i> case)	Introduction of inter-platform “rivalry” into the market	Excessive data disclosure; intrusion on a third person’s privacy	
Self-preferencing (ATT policy)	Costs in relation to privacy protection are fully disclosed	Lack of transparency in hidden charges or costs	

Conclusion

This paper considers privacy as a construction, in which the parts - including conception of privacy, free flow of information, the priority of invasion of privacy claims, the consent and autonomy, the privacy expectations, and the competitive environment – blend and harmonize with one another.

Guided by such a rationale, this paper seeks to fill the gap in the consent system by introducing an assurance – the validity of consent to a data processing is premised on the fulfillment of individual’s reasonable expectations of privacy, which is not variable; we need not to consent for everything, but we can ascertain whether our data would be accessed to in the way we expect even absent a consent, or even a request.

In this vision, our consents are not only contextually connected with our expectations; we could trust our consents and allow the access to our information when the technology is innovated in our favor (the first context), expect for those we specially care and we positively reject (the second context)– we have to trust them, unless we are coerced by power (the third context), or induced by “free of charge” (the fourth context).

Last but not least, as the personal information interacts with and incorporates into many private or public interests in the digital world, all the values and instruments, such as technological innovation, right to data portability, fiduciary duty, risk assessment, objective justification, etc., taken into account in the balancing test, should not deviate from individual autonomy.

¹ Samuel D. Warren & Louis D. Brandeis, *The Right to Privacy*, 5 HARV. L. REV. 193, 207 (1890).

² James Q. Whitman, *The Two Western Cultures of Privacy: Dignity versus Liberty*, 113 YALE L.J. 1151, 1161 (2004).

³ Edward J. Bloustein, *Privacy as An Aspect of Human Dignity: An Answer to Dean Prosser*, 39 N.Y.U.L.REV. 962, 1000–07 (1964); Bart van der Sloot, *Privacy as Personality Right: Why the ECtHR's Focus on Ulterior Interests Might Prove Indispensable in the Age of "Big Data,"* 31 UTRECHT JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL AND EUROPEAN LAW 25, 26 (2015).

⁴ Matthew Tokson, *The Emerging Principles of Fourth Amendment Privacy*, 88 GEO. WASH. L. REV. 1, 54 (2020); Brian Mund, *Social Media Searches and the Reasonable Expectation of Privacy*, 19 YALE J.L. & TECH. 238, 250–52 (2017).

⁵ If authorization is required and has been given, the gates are up; if authorization is required and has not been given, the gates are down. However, it left unanswered the important question of whether this inquiry turns only on technological (or “code-based,” which is easy to accomplish) limitations on access, or instead also looks to limits contained in contracts or policies. See *Van Buren v. United States*, No. 19-783, at 13 n.8.

⁶ *hiQ Labs, Inc. v. LinkedIn Corp.*, D.C. No.3:17-cv-03301-EMC, at 18 (9th Cir. Apr. 18, 2022).

⁷ E.g. *Rotaru v. Romania* [GC], no. 28341/95, §§ 43–44, ECHR 2000–V; *P.G. and J.H. v. the United Kingdom*, no. 44787/98, § 56, ECHR 2001–IX; *Peck v. the United Kingdom*, no. 44647/98, §§ 57–60, ECHR 2003–I.

⁸ Art. 7 EUCFR provides that everyone has “right to respect for his private and family life, his home and his correspondence”; Art. 8 EUCFR provides that everyone has “the right to the protection of personal data concerning him or her”.

⁹ E.g., *Zhuye v. Baidu, Inc.*, Civil Judgment of Jiangsu Nanjing Intermediate People's Court, Case No. (2014) Ning Min Zhong No. 5028.

¹⁰ E.g., *Dianping.com v. Aibang, Inc.*, Civil Judgment of Beijing First Intermediate People's Court, Case No. (2011) Yi Zhong Min Zhong No. 7512.

¹¹ *In re Facebook, Inc. Internet Tracking Litig.*, 956 F. 3d 589 (9th Cir. 2020). We will discuss this case in Section III.

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- ¹² Ignacio N. Cofone & Adriana Z. Robertson, *Privacy Harms*, 69 HASTINGS L.J. 1039 (2017).
- ¹³ U.S. Federal Trade Commission [FTC], *Data Brokers: A Call for Transparency and Accountability*, 55-56 (May 2014), <https://www.ftc.gov/system/files/documents/reports/data-brokers-call-transparency-accountability-report-federal-trade-commission-may-2014/140527databrokerreport.pdf>.
- ¹⁴ Jerry Kang, *Information Privacy in Cyberspace Transactions*, 50 STANFORD LAW REVIEW 1193, 1202-11 (1998).
- ¹⁵ Bert-Jaap Koops, et al., *A Typology of Privacy*, 38 U. PA. J. INT'L L. 483, 566-69 (2017).
- ¹⁶ From the electronic listening device in *Katz*, to the GPS tracking device in *Jones* and *Carpenter*, the courts recognized that current doctrinal protections (e.g. third-party doctrine) do not “fit neatly” with modern forms of digital data. See Evan H. Caminker, *Location Tracking and Digital Data: Can Carpenter Build a Stable Privacy Doctrine?* 2018 SUPREME COURT REVIEW 411, 430 (2018).
- ¹⁷ *United States v. Jones*, 132 S.Ct. 945, 955 (2012).
- ¹⁸ Mund, *supra* note 4, at 258.
- ¹⁹ Gabrielle S. Friedman & James Q. Whitman, *The European Transformation of Harassment Law: Discrimination Versus Dignity*, 9 COLUM. J. EUR. L. 241, 241-67 (2003).
- ²⁰ Raphaël Gellert & Serge Gutwirth, *The legal construction of privacy and data protection*, 29 COMPUT. LAW SECUR. REV. 522, 526 (2013).
- ²¹ Lee A. Bygrave, *The Place of Privacy in Data Protection Law*, 24 UNSW LAW JOURNAL 277, 277-82 (2001).
- ²² Mary Madden, et al., *Privacy, Poverty, and Big Data: A Matrix of Vulnerabilities for Poor Americans*, 95 WASH. U. L. REV. 53, 65-67 (2017).
- ²³ Elena Gil González & Paul de Hert, *Understanding the legal provisions that allow processing and profiling of personal data—an analysis of GDPR provisions and principles*, 19 ERA FORUM 597, 610 (2019).
- ²⁴ There is possibility that the two parties hold property interests in the same data, especially when business investment is added to the processing, and natural person should be entitled to the economic value coming out of their own “raw materials,” compared to those data harvesters.
- ²⁵ According to Article 82(1) GDPR, “any person who has suffered *material or non-material* damage as a result of an infringement of this Regulation shall have the right to receive compensation from the controller or processor for the damage suffered”; in cases, such as *Lindqvist*, people breached data protection law for privacy invasion without identifying material harms. See *Lindqvist v Åklagarkammaren i Jönköping*, C-101/01, [2003] ECLI:EU:C:2003:596.
- ²⁶ I will elaborate on these three cases in Section III.
- ²⁷ Patrik Hiselius, *ICT/Internet and the Right to Privacy*, 56 SCANDINAVIAN STUDIES IN LAW 201, 203 (2010); Lee A. Bygrave, *Privacy Protection in a Global Context – A Comparative Overview*, 47 SCANDINAVIAN STUDIES IN LAW 319, 321-22 (2004).
- ²⁸ Sloot, *supra* note 3, at 27.
- ²⁹ Ignacio N. Cofone, *Beyond Data Ownership*, 43 CARDOZO LAW REVIEW 501, 525-27 (2021).
- ³⁰ *Id.*, at 527.
- ³¹ For example, marketing purposes with details such as storing the preferences of users may be regarded as legitimate. See Administrative Penalty Decision of Belgian Data Protection Authority, Case No. [2022] No. DOS-2019-01377. A trade association IAB Europe

established a Transparency & Consent Framework (TCF) for communication in the adtech industry, but got penalized by Belgian authority.

³² *Digi Távközlési és Szolgáltató Kft. v. Nemzeti Adatvédelmi és Információszabadság Hatóság*, Case C-77/21, ECLI:EU:C:2022:805 (Oct. 20, 2022), <https://curia.europa.eu/juris/liste.jsf?num=C-77/21>.

³³ Helen Nissenbaum, *Privacy as Contextual Integrity*, 79 WASH. L. REV. 119, 141 (2004).

³⁴ Rachel Metz, *A beginner's guide to Mastodon, the Twitter alternative that's on fire*, CNN BUSINESS (Nov. 8, 2022), <https://edition.cnn.com/2022/11/08/tech/mastodon-twitter-explainer-trnd/index.html>; Jordan Palmer, *What is Mastodon - the Hottest Twitter Alternative Explained*, TOM'S GUIDE (Nov. 3, 2022), <https://www.tomsguide.com/reference/what-is-mastodon-why-people-are-fleeing-elon-musks-twitter-for-this-social-network>.

³⁵ For example, most services will now let you download your own social media posts, but what about other people's comments to those posts, or your comments and tags on other people's posts and photos? See Comments of New America's Open Technology Institute, *In re Competition and Consumer Protection in the 21st Century: The Intersection Between Privacy, Big Data, and Competition*, at 4 (Aug. 20, 2018), https://www.ftc.gov/system/files/documents/public_comments/2018/08/ftc-2018-0051-d0034-154926.pdf.

³⁶ Orin Kerr, *The Case for the Third-Party Doctrine*, 107 MICH. L. REV. 561, 587–90 (2009).

³⁷ E.g., *Carpenter v. United States*, 138 S. Ct. 2206, 2217 (2018); *United States v. Jones*, 565 U.S. 400, 404–07 (2012).

³⁸ Neil Richards & Woodrow Hartzog, *The Pathologies of Digital Consent*, 96 WASH. U. L. REV. 1461, 1466 (2019).

³⁹ Some scholars argue that humans are not merely irrational, but predictably so. See DAN ARIELY, *PREDICTABLY IRRATIONAL: THE HIDDEN FORCES THAT SHAPE OUR DECISIONS* (2008).

⁴⁰ Susan Freiwald & Stephen Wm. Smith, *The Carpenter Chronicle*, 132 HARV. L. REV. 205, 220 (2018).

⁴¹ As such, lack of transparency in the costs arising from standardization, for example, may also lead to inconsistency with REP, for user who opts in a “privacy-friendly” scheme without genuinely knowing the cost.

⁴² Cofone, *supra* note 29, at 564–67.

⁴³ Raphaël Gellert & Serge Gutwirth, *The legal construction of privacy and data protection*, 29 COMPUT. LAW SECUR. REV. 522, 529 (2013).

⁴⁴ Facebook pointed out, in its report, there were tough questions about whether and, if so, how the data of “non-requesting users” should be transferred. See The Facebook Company, Comments to the FTC on Data Portability (2020), <https://about.fb.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Facebook-Comments-to-FTC-on-Data-Portability.pdf> (last visited Dec. 1, 2022).

⁴⁵ Art. 29 Data Protection Working Party, Guidelines on the Right to Data Portability, 16/EN WP 242 rev.01, 12 (Apr. 5, 2017), <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/just/redirection/document/44099>.

⁴⁶ Civil Judgment of Shanghai Intellectual Property Court, Case No. (2016) Hu 73 Min Zhong No. 242.

⁴⁷ Chinese courts usually elaborate on alternative or substitution effect to plaintiff's market share resulting from the defendant's act in the anti-unfair competition cases.

⁴⁸ It may come to a different conclusion in different legal contexts. This paper regards these information as personal information in that they reveal one's preferences and even income levels, which will contribute to profiling.

⁴⁹ Chinese courts usually attach much importance on free-riding to the business ethic, as a court states, "it is inappropriate to free use the *business investments* developed by others instead of their own in the course of competition." Therefore, free use of business investments from platforms without consent or paying remuneration is free-riding and immoral. See Wei Liu & Ping Chen, *Justification of the behavior regulatory pattern on data scraping*, 43 COMPUT. LAW SECUR. REV. 1, 8-9 (2021).

⁵⁰ Cofone, *supra* note 29, at 567.

⁵¹ Fruits of labor, obtained by legitimate efforts, is one of the objectives protected by Chinese AUCL, which means fair competition should defer to the principles of honesty and good faith.

⁵² *Perfect 10, Inc. v. Amazon.com, Inc., et al.*, 508 F.3d 1146 (9th Cir. 2007).

⁵³ *Id.*, see *Kelly v. Arriba Soft Corp.*, 336 F.3d 811, 816 (9th Cir. 2003).

⁵⁴ Information Commissioner's Office [ICO], What is the 'legitimate interests' basis? https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/legitimate-interests/what-is-the-legitimate-interests-basis/#reasonable_expectations (last visited Dec. 3, 2022).

⁵⁵ *hiQ Labs, Inc. v. LinkedIn Corp.*, No. 17-16783 (9th Cir. 2022).

⁵⁶ *hiQ Labs, Inc. v. LinkedIn Corp.* (N.D. Cal. Aug. 14, 2017).

⁵⁷ According to the Footnote 3 of the order granted by the district court, though the "Do Not Broadcast" feature makes it less likely to draw immediate attention to a profile update, it does nothing to prevent an employer, or any other third-party, from visiting an employee's page periodically to determine whether significant changes have been made. See *id.*, n.3.

⁵⁸ *Katz v. United States*, 389 U.S. 347 (1967).

⁵⁹ *Id.*, at 361 (Harlan, J., concurring).

⁶⁰ *Carpenter v. United States*, 138 S. Ct. 2206 (2018).

⁶¹ Peter Winn, *Katz and the Origins of the "Reasonable Expectation of Privacy" Test*, 40 MCGEORGE L. REV. 1, 8 (2009); Orin S. Kerr, *Katz Has Only One Step: The Irrelevance of Subjective Expectations*, 82 U CHI L REV. 113, 113-34 (2015); Caminker, *supra* note 16, at 440.

⁶² Information Commissioner's Office [ICO], What is the 'legitimate interests' basis? https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/legitimate-interests/what-is-the-legitimate-interests-basis/#reasonable_expectations (last visited Dec. 3, 2022).

⁶³ With regard to Supreme Court's certiorari in LinkedIn, commentators raised the concern that companies wishing to prohibit scraping may need to consider whether to require a password to access some or all of the data so that it is clear when the "gates are down," as well as contemplate other anti-scraping causes of action as part of their litigation strategies. See Randi Singer & Michael Goodyear, *Scraping Suit Stymied after Van Buren* (June 16, 2021), <https://www.weil.com/-/media/mailings/2021/q2/scraping-suit-stymied-after-van-buren.pdf>.

⁶⁴ Paul M. Schwartz, *Property, Privacy, and Personal Data*, 117 HARV. L. REV. 2056, 2107 (2004).

⁶⁵ Erika M. Douglast, *Monopolization Remedies and Data Privacy*, 24 VA. J.L. & TECH. 1, 49-

53 (2020).

⁶⁶ *hiQ Labs, Inc. v. LinkedIn Corp.*, 938 F.3d 985, 994 (9th Cir. 2019).

⁶⁷ *In re Facebook, Inc. Internet Tracking Litig.*, *supra* note 11.

⁶⁸ For example, a pervasive and constant facial recognition tracking in public spaces would likely be a Fourth Amendment search. See Tokson, *supra* note 4, at 55-57.

⁶⁹ *Facebook, Inc. v. Bundeskartellamt*, No. 080/2020 (BGH. Jun. 23, 2020), <https://www.bundesgerichtshof.de/SharedDocs/Pressemitteilungen/DE/2020/2020080.html>.

⁷⁰ Via the analytical and statistical functions of “Facebook Analytics,” the companies receive aggregated data on how Facebook users interact with the services they offer across various devices, platforms and websites.

⁷¹ *Facebook*, *supra* note 69.

⁷² Richards & Hartzog, *supra* note 38, at 1466.

⁷³ Kirsten Martin, *Privacy Notices as Tabula Rasa: An Empirical Investigation into How Complying with a Privacy Notice is Related to Meeting Privacy Expectations Online*, 34 J. PUBLIC POLICY MARK. 210, 210-27 (2015).

⁷⁴ It is disputable that simplified language cannot provide enough detail to give complete information. See Solon Barocas & Helen Nissenbaum, *Big data's end run around anonymity and consent*. in PRIVACY, BIG DATA AND THE PUBLIC GOOD 44 (2014).

⁷⁵ David Meyer, *France Refuses to Block Apple's Big Privacy Changes*, FORTUNE (Mar. 17, 2021), <https://fortune.com/2021/03/17/apple-privacy-changes-app-tracking-antitrust-france>.

⁷⁶ Suzanne Vranica, et al., *Inside Facebook's \$10 Billion Breakup with Advertisers*, WALL STREET JOURNAL, Feb. 19, 2022, https://www.wsj.com/amp/articles/facebook-apple-google-advertising-privacy-changes-11645199877?mod=tech_lead_pos3; Brandon Vigliarolo, *Apple App Transparency Changes Bring in the Ad Bucks...for Apple*, THE REGISTER (Sep. 6, 2022), https://www.theregister.com/2022/09/06/apple_app_transparency_ad_revenues.

⁷⁷ The Apple Company, *User Privacy and Data Use* (2022), <https://developer.apple.com/app-store/user-privacy-and-data-use> (last visited Dec. 3, 2022).

⁷⁸ Competition and Markets Authority [CMA], *Online Platforms and Digital Advertising market study, Appendix G: the role of tracking in digital advertising* (2020), at para. 357, https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5fe49554e90e0711ffe07d05/Appendix_G_-_Tracking_and_PETS_v.16_non-confidential_WEB.pdf.

⁷⁹ The Apple Company, *Mobile Advertising and the Impact of Apple's App Tracking Transparency Policy* (2022), https://www.apple.com/privacy/docs/Mobile_Advertising_and_the_Impact_of_Apples_App_Tracking_Transparency_Policy_April_2022.pdf.

⁸⁰ Jessica Davies, *WTF are Shared Identity Solutions?* DIGIDAY (Sep. 23, 2019), <https://digiday.com/media/what-are-shared-identity-solutions-and-can-they-really-replace-cookies>.

⁸¹ Damien Geradin, et al., *Google as a de facto Privacy Regulator: Analysing the Privacy Sandbox from An Antitrust Perspective*, 17 EUROPEAN COMPETITION JOURNAL 617, 636-37 (2021).

⁸² The second scenario is much more like an “open” interoperable system, which I will discuss in the following part.

⁸³ E.g., Facebook’s Download Your Info, Google Takeout. See Inge Graef & Martin Husovec & Nadezhda Purtova, *Data Portability and Data Control: Lessons for an Emerging Concept*

in *EU Law*, 19 GERMAN LAW JOURNAL 1359, 1386 (2018).

⁸⁴ Wolfgang Kerber, *Data Governance in Connected Cars: The Problem of Access to In-Vehicle Data*, 9 J. INTELL. PROP. INFO. TECH. & ELEC. COM. L. 310, 326-27 (2018).

⁸⁵ Herbert Zech, *A Legal Framework for a Data Economy in the European Digital Single Market: Rights to Use Data*, 11 JOURNAL OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY LAW & PRACTICE 460, 460-470 (2016).

⁸⁶ Schwartz, *supra* note 64, at 2103-04.

⁸⁷ For example, commit on a cease-tracking outside platform but violate it, intended for research purposes only but used for crime detection; for the latter, e.g., GEDmatch, see Familytree, GEDmatch Updated Its Privacy Policy, <https://www.familytree.com/blog/gedmatch-updated-its-privacy-policy> (last visited Dec. 3, 2022); see also Natalie Ram, *Genetic Privacy After Carpenter*, 105 VA. L. REV. 1357, 1411-17 (2019).

⁸⁸ Both individual profiling and group profiling can lead to high risks of unfairness. See González & Hert, *supra* note 23, at 608-11.